

NDAC/LO/111
1988 Aug 24

25th NDAC Report from Lund Observatory

WP6000: Step 2/3 (Lindegren)

Most of the work performed in June to August was devoted to the programme ANAL23 which will be used to analyse the results of the sphere reconstitution and determination of astrometric parameters. The programme contains a number of facilities for statistical and graphical analysis and comparison of two star catalogues, *e.g.* the Input Catalogue and the one resulting from the Step 2/3 process. However, the programme may also be useful at a later stage for comparing the FAST and NDAC catalogues.

WP8000: Double Stars (Söderhjelm)

Certain systematic effects previously found in the photometric results for binaries with separation less than 10 arcsec were found to be due to a programme error. This is now corrected and new reductions have been made in which most of the systematic errors have disappeared (C).

As previously reported, procedures for the standard double star analysis (STDDBL) are now well established and have been tested extensively. Attention is now focused on the analysis of multiple stars (STDMUL), and a first report on these simulations is soon to appear.

Working paper:

C = NDAC/LO/110 (Söderhjelm, 1988 June 20):
HIPPARCOS reductions for multiple stars, VIc